

RESEARCH ARTICLE ↓

Effect of Current Asset Management on The Financial Performance of Manufacturing Firm Southeast Nigeria*Authors*

Nwachukwu, Basilia Chiamaka PhD and Echefu, Silas Chinweze PhD

Authors	Affiliation
1 st	Department of Accountancy, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu State, Nigeria
2 nd	Department of Accounting/Finance Spiritan University, Nneochi, Abia State

Abstract

The study examined the Effect of Current Asset Management on the Financial Performance of Manufacturing Firm Southeast Nigeria. The liquid assets variables studied comprises Account Receivables (AR), and Short-Term Investment (STI) while the Operational Performance variable studied is Turnover (TNV). Secondary data were sourced from the annual reports of the firms under review. Two Hypotheses were estimated with the use of Random Effect Panel Multi Regression Analyses. The findings of the study show that: Short Term Investment (STI) have positive and significant relationship on the Turnover (TNV) of the industrial goods sectors in Nigeria and have a moderate and very weak positive on consumer goods sector while Account Receivables (AR) has a weak positive relationship on turnover of the consumer goods sector has a moderate positive relationship on the performance of industrial and consumer goods sector in Nigeria. This implies that organization without adequate liquid asset is bound to suffer set back (difficult to meet short term obligation). Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concludes that a well-managed, account receivables will lead to improvement of operational performance in Industrial goods sectors, while in the consumer goods sector among the explanatory variables can predict operational performance effectively. The researcher recommend that management should put more attention on their current assets management in order to maintain an adequate performance in the sectors.

Keywords: *Current Asset Management; Financial Management; Manufacturing Firm; Industrial Goods Sectors; Consumers Goods Sectors; Southeast Nigeria*

Introduction

Current asset management refers to all the actions and decisions of the management which affects the size and effectiveness of current asset. Current asset management requires special attention in present days when cost of capital is rising and funds are scarce (Yahaya, Kutigi, Solanke, Onyabe and Usman, 2015). It has been generally established that the performance/profitability of a firm largely depends upon the manner of its current asset management. If a firm is inefficient in managing current asset, it will not only reduce profitability but may also lead to financial crisis. Both inadequate and excessive current asset is detrimental for a firm (Yahaya, Kutigi, Solanke, Onyabe and Usman, 2015). Excessive current asset can result in idle funds which could be used for earning profit while the inadequate current asset will interrupt the operations and will also impair profitability (Chowdhary & Amin, 2007). For several organizations, current assets management can make or mar the organization's financial performance. Financial performance measures are used as indicators to evaluate the success of any business venture. It is the primary concern of business organization to determine which assets to give significant attention to enhance the return on assets. Performance is the bottom-line for every organization, business and non-business alike. It is essential because non-performance can spell failure. Financial performance is a subjective measure of how well a firm can use assets from its primary and non-primary modes of business and generate revenues. The term, financial performance, is also used as a general measure of a firm's overall financial health over a given period. It can be used to compare similar firms across the same industry or to compare industries or sectors in aggregation. In broader sense, financial performance refers to the degree to which financial objectives being or has been accomplished. It is the process of measuring the results of a firm's policies and operations in monetary terms (Yahaya, Kutigi, Solanke, Onyabe and Usman, 2015; Eniola & Memba, 2016). There are different ways to measure financial performance, but all measures should be taken in aggregation. All organizations have financial performance measures as part of their performance management, although there is debate as to the relative importance of financial and non-financial indicators. Proponents of financial performance measures argue that they are necessary because of the primary objectives of firms (Kaplan Financial, 2015). Line items such as gross revenue from operations, operating income or cash flow from operations can be used, as well as return on total assets.

Statement of the Problem

The contribution of quoted firms to the economy of a country such as Nigeria is enormous. Several companies, however, are experiencing declining performance and some have even been delisted from the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NGSE) in the last decade. This is to the expectations of their stakeholders who span across shareholders, employees, consumers, and government among others. Companies in Nigeria, especially in the industrial and consumer goods sectors are still in a developing stage. Thus, they need adequate short-term investments and finance for expansion of their operational activities. Managing cash is a real challenge to financial managers in Nigerian firms. International financial reporting standards adoption requires that current assets are classified into inventories, trade receivables, other receivables and prepayments, cash and bank balances. Thus, firms have adequate liquid assets (Cash, Bank) in the direction to meet the payment program by comparing the cash and near-cash among the payment obligations.

Objectives of the Study

The study examined the Effect of Current Asset Management on the Financial Performance of Manufacturing Firm Southeast Nigeria. The specific objectives tend to;

- I. Assess the relationship between account receivables and turnover of quoted industrial and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria
- II. Evaluate the relationship between short term investments and turnover of quoted industrial and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria's.

Statement of Hypotheses

- I. Account receivables do not significantly relate to turnover of quoted industrial and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria
- II. Short term investments do not connect with turnover of quoted industrial and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Asset Management

Asset management is concerned with the efficient utilization of the organization's investment in both physical and human asset to guarantee profit maximization objective of the firm. The term asset refers to those assets such as: investments (stock, bonds), accounts receivable, inventory which in the ordinary course of business can be, or will be, converted into cash without undergoing a diminution in value and without disrupting the operations of the firm. The prime object of management is to make profit (Eniola and Memba, 2016). This accomplishment in most business depends largely on the way they manage their assets. Administration of fixed assets falls within the realm of capital budgeting while the management of working capital is a continuing function which involves control of every day and flow of financial resources circulating in the company in one form or the other. In turn, these decisions are influenced by the trade-off that must be made between profitability and risk. Asset management deals with the financial health of a company and it also plays important role in maximizing the shareholders wealth, hence, every company needs to sustain the balance between liquidity and profitability (Eniola and Memba, 2016). Asset's structure has been defined using various aspects by different scholars based on the direction of the study. According to Zheng Sheng and NuoZhi (2013) asset structure is the allocation of the resources diversely. It can be broken down into 3 components namely: turnover assets, production assets and wasting assets. Koralun-Bereznicka (2013) in Mwaniki and Omagwa (2017) described asset structure as a combination of the various asset components which were identified as: financial fixed assets; tangible fixed assets; current assets; and current investments and cash in hand and at bank. A similar approach is taken by, Mwaniki and Omagwa (2017) where asset structure is described in terms of: current assets; long term investments and funds; Property, Plant and Equipment; intangible assets; and other assets. Mwaniki and Omagwa (2017) studied the assets structure conceptualizing it as component of fixed assets as current assets. Empirical evidence has concluded that the study of asset structure is significant to the business organizations. Zheng Sheng and Nuo Zhi (2013) contends that the research of assets structure has more practical value and universal significance than capital structure as they are the main source of creating corporate value and avoid risks. Olatunji and Tajudeen (2014) found that investments in fixed assets have strong and positive statistical impact on the profitability of banking sector in Nigeria. Asset's structure has also been widely reported by corporate finance literature to significantly affect financial structure of firm (Koralun-Bereznicka, 2013).

Accounts Receivable

The study of the effect of receivables management on corporate profitability has become necessary because many organizations have fallen victims of premature death. This is because of inadequate attention paid to account receivables. Receivable management is very important for all business be it small or large (Duru, Ekwe and Okpe, 2014). The extent to which firms manage their receivables go a long way to the level of their profit because of customers who have not yet made payment for consumer goods sector and services which the firms has provided. The management of accounts receivable is largely influenced by the credit policy and collection procedure. A credit policy specifies requirement to value the worth of customers and a collection procedure provides guidelines to collect unpaid invoice that will reduce delays for customers who have not yet made payment for consumer goods sector and services and outstanding receivable, (Duru, Ekwe and Okpe, 2014). Account receivable represents the average days that firm takes to collect payment from its customers (Falope and Ayilore, 2009; and shams and Kumar, 2011 in Duru, Ekwe and Okpe, 2014). Excessive level of current assets and low level of current assets may lead to negative effect on a firm's profitability and difficulties in mediating smooth operation. The relevance of management

of account receivables to firm performance is deemed necessary because of the frequency of corporate failure in Nigeria in recent times owing to improper management of accounts receivables and hence, this study. Accounts receivable measures the unpaid claims a firm has over its customers at a given time, usually comes in the form of operating line of credit and is mainly due within a relatively short time period (up to one year). The volume of accounts receivable indicates firm's supply of trade credit (Denčić-Mihajlov, 2011). Accounts receivables are one of the most important parts of working capital. Receivables often represent large investment in asset and involve significant volume of transactions and decisions. In different theories, the existence of receivables is explained by commercial reasons, transaction-cost motivations, and financial incentives (Marotta, 2005; Petersen & Rajan, 1997).

Short Term Investment

Short-term investment is principally concerned with the breakdown of results that affect current assets and current liabilities. It involves multiple crucial results, which encompass management of account payables and receivables, cash conversion cycle, preservation a definite level of stock and the investment of available cash (Deloof, 2003). Result about working capital management are generally associated with simultaneous financing of short-term investments of both current assets and current liabilities. Hence, short term financial management is reasonably termed working capital management most of the time. The performance of working capital suggests an important assessment of the state of the financial position of a company. Companies can cut necessity on external funding by efficiently managing working capital, and employ the autonomous cash for additional investments, which results in added financial flexibility. A firm needs to retain a certain level of net working capital in order to obtain debt financing from most financial institutions. Thus, short-term financial management for the most part is the fundamental occupation of corporate management since it is a life-giving force for any business. For that reason, both profit and non-profit leaning organizations, regardless of their size and business type, needs a certain level of working capital. Financial decisions of short-term assets and liabilities management are critical because they lay bare the financial stability of the firm and the market. These decisions moreover ensure that a business has ample cash flow to take care of operating expenses and short-term debt obligations. The working capital components carry with it benefits and costs. For example, inventory holding lessens stock-out situations but raises the carrying costs. Conversely, holding insufficient inventory could lead to loss of sales, benevolence among customers and production interruptions.

Financial Performance

Financial performance is often measured using traditional accounting key performance indicators such as return on assets, operating profit margin, earnings before interest and tax, economic value added or sales growth. The advantage of these measurements is their general availability, since every profit-oriented organization produces these figures for the yearly financial reporting. However, statement of financial position manipulations and choices of accounting methods may also lead to values that allow only limited comparability of the financial strength of companies. This study develops a composite index by getting the simple average of gross profit margin. The gross profit margin or the gross margin is a financial metric used to assess a firm's financial health by revealing the proportion of money left over from turnover after accounting for the cost of consumer goods sector sold. Gross profit margin serves as the source for paying additional expenses and future savings. The gross margin is not an exact estimate of the company's pricing strategy but it does give a good indication of financial health. Without an adequate gross margin, a company will be unable to pay its operating and other expenses and build for the future. Firm performance is determined by profitability measures. From a financial performance standpoint, a company can be said to be performing well if it makes greater use of its assets than its rivals or competitors (Morara and Sibindi 2021). Al-Abass (2018) states that profitability is made up of two words: profit and ability. Profit refers to the total income or return from a business, while ability refers to the power that is used by the business to earn profit and how efficiently management makes this profit by utilizing all available resources. Among the available resources a company has is the efficient management of working capital to generate positive returns. Profitability is the excess of revenue over costs, which generates a higher internal rate of return.

Theoretical Review

Assumptions of Trade Off Theory

- (1) The basic assumption of this theory is that holding cash neither creates nor destroys value (Myer 1984)
- (2) The firm can always raise funds from capital markets when funds are needed without transaction cost.
- (3) The trade-off theory suggests that firms target an optimal level of liquidity to balance the benefit and cost of holding cash.

The cost of holding cash includes low rate of return of these assets because of liquidity premium and possibly tax disadvantage. The benefits of holding cash are in two-fold:

- i. The firms save transaction costs to raise funds and do not need to liquidate assets to make payments.
- ii. The firm can use liquid assets to finance its activities and investment if other sources of funding are not available or are extremely expensive.

An efficient working capital is achieved when there is a trade-off between liquidity and profitability and the shareholders' value (Dash & Hanuman, 2008). Efficiency in working capital management seeks to ensure that the investment in working capital components is neither too little nor too high. The former could give rise to illiquidity, stock outs, and lost sales, whereas the latter amounts to waste. With regards to profitability, the level of investment in working capital and the financing of this investment, at any particular level of output, involve a risk-return trade-off (Raheman and Nasr, 2007). Generally, the higher the risk the higher the return will be demanded by management and shareholders in order to finance any investment in working capital. When the liquid assets requirements are not properly managed and are allocated more than required, it renders the management inefficient and reduces the benefits of short-term investments. On the other hand, if the liquid asset is too low, the company may miss a lot of profitable opportunities or suffer short-term liquidity crisis, leading to the degradation of company credit, as it cannot respond effectively to temporary capital requirements. There may be various external and internal factors that may induce the firms to strike a balance between meeting unforeseen capital requirements and avoiding inefficient management of capital.

Keynesian Liquidity Preference Theory

Keynesian liquidity preference theory is another theory underpinning working capital management which was propounded by economist John Keynes in 1936. The theory postulated that as other things are kept constant, investors prefer liquid investments to illiquid ones and there is always demand for premium on investments that have longer maturity periods. According to this theory people hold cash or inventory for these motives namely; for transaction, speculative, precaution, and compensation motives. The need for working capital to run the day-to-day business activities is an indispensable obligation. Firms needs to make enough funds available for current asset to enhance successful running of their business activities (Abuzayed, 2016).

Empirical Review

Ramana, Ramakrishnaiah and Chengalrayulu (2013) attempted to study the impact of receivables management on working capital and profitability using data collected from the annual reports of selected cement companies from 2001 to 2010. The ratios which highlight the efficiency of receivables management viz., receivables to current assets ratio, receivables to total assets ratio, receivables to sales ratio, receivables turnover ratio, average collection period, working capital ratio and profitability ratio. Applying the ANOVA, the test result shows that the receivable management across cement industry is efficient and showing significant impact on working capital and profitability. Denčić-Mihajlov (2011) investigates how public companies listed at the regulated market in the Republic of Serbia manage their accounts receivables during the recession times using a sample of 108 firms which are the most successful Serbian firms listed at the Prime and Standard Listing as well as the Multilateral Trading Platform of the Belgrade Stock Exchange. The accounts receivables policies were examined in the crisis period of 2008-2011. To explore the relation between accounts receivables and firm's profitability, the short-term effects were tested using

a regression analysis. The study shows that between accounts receivables and two dependent variables on profitability, return on total asset and operating profit margin, there is a positive but no significant relation. Abdulazeez et al. (2018) examines the impact of working capital management on the financial performance of listed conglomerate companies in Nigeria for a period of ten (10) years (2005-2014). Data for the study were quantitatively retrieved from the annual reports and accounts of the studied companies. The study employed descriptive statistics to describe the variable while the relationships among the variables were established via correlation. Variable Inflation Factor (VIF) was used to determine the existence or otherwise of multi-collinearity while Ordinary Least Square (OLS) Regression was used to analyze the data. It was found that debtors collection period, creditors payment period and firm size were negatively related to return on investment while cash conversion cycle has positive but insignificant relationship with the financial performance of the studied companies. The study however, recommends among others that listed conglomerate companies should maintain the current debtors' collection period or further reduce it in order to continue to enhance financial performance. Micheal, Segun and Taiwo, (2017), in their study examined the impact of working capital management on financial performance of quoted consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria by specifically examined the impact of working capital management on return on assets and gross operating profit. The secondary data used were obtained from annual financial statements over a period of ten (10) years from 2005 to 2014 of purposively sampled fifteen (15) firms. Descriptive statistics were used to measure variations, statistical inferences were drawn using correlation and panel regression analysis was applied on performance and working capital management indicators to test the formulated hypotheses. The findings revealed that efficient working capital management increases financial performance. In conclusion, a negative relationship exists between Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) and financial performance while there is a positive relationship between creditors' payment period; debtors' collection period and financial performance.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this research is the *ex-post facto* research design. This means that the events that was investigated had already taken place and thus data already exist. The adoption of this research design hinged on three (3) reasons. (1) that the study relied on historic accounting data; (2) that the data was obtained from the financial statements and accounts of firms; (3) that the sampled firms were quoted on the Nigeria Stock Exchange, and as such the event under investigation had already taken place. The researcher studied all public industrial good sectors and consumer goods sectors that their stocks are quoted on the Nigerian Exchange group. However, for the analysis, the study focused on the industrial and consumer goods sectors. The secondary data was sourced from the published financial statements and accounts of sampled firms quoted on the Nigeria Stock Exchange. The firm sampled is Berger Paint Plc. Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to measure the linear correlation between two variables. Only firm specific factors are analyzed and tested given that only firm data from firms in Nigeria are used. To reduce the effect of extreme values, variables with such characteristics are deflated using total assets. The reliability and validity of the stated models depends wholly on the satisfaction of these theoretical underpinnings.

Model Specification

The model that was adapted from Nwaogwugwu (2005) in his analysis of the influence of fiscal deficit on the performance of the Nigeria economy and it was modified to suite this research work as this.

$$TNV = f (AR + STI)$$

Were,

TNR = Turnover

AR = Account Receivables

STI=Short term investment

Expressing the above functional relationship with control variable in a linear regression model, we have

$$TNR_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AR_{it} + \beta_2 STI_{it}$$

Where;

β_0 is the constant and intercept
 β_1 , and β_2 are model parameters to be estimated.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Data Analysis

Industrial Goods Firms

Table 1: Descriptive Statistic of the Industrial Goods Firms

	<i>TNR</i>	<i>AR01</i>	<i>STI_PP</i>
<i>Mean</i>	377923.7	37655.09	167950.9
<i>Median</i>	145864.0	11106.50	5187.500
<i>Maximum</i>	1500112.	318463.0	2387695.
<i>Minimum</i>	2901.000	283.0000	2.000000
<i>Std. Dev.</i>	468937.9	65089.79	472067.4
<i>Skewness</i>	1.089068	2.309107	3.256872
<i>Kurtosis</i>	2.769975	8.389121	13.01295
<i>Jarque-Bera</i>	10.79368	113.3337	321.0480
<i>Probability</i>	0.004531	0.000000	0.000000
<i>Sum</i>	20407881	2033375.	9069347.
<i>Sum Sq. Dev.</i>	1.17E+13	2.25E+11	1.18E+13
<i>Observations</i>	54	54	54

Source: Computed by Researcher Using E-views 10.0 Statistical Software

The normality of the distribution of the data series is shown by the coefficients of Skewness, Kurtosis, and the probability values of the Jaque-Bera test for normality. From the Table 1, the probability of the Jaque-Bera statistics for all the variables (dependent and independent) have significant p-values. They are as follows Turnover (0.004531), Account Receivables (0.00000), and Short-term Investments (0.00000). The significance of p-values depicts a non-normal distribution for both the focal and explanatory variables. This was further confirmed by the skewness coefficients which are all greater than one for all the variables. The kurtosis coefficient provides a second level of confirmation that all the variables have a non-normal distribution with the Kurtosis coefficients exceeding three.

Table 2: Result of Panel Unit Root Tests (ADF-Type Unit Root Tests)

<i>Null Hypothesis: the variable has a unit root</i>		<i>TNR</i>	<i>AR01</i>	<i>STI_PP</i>
		At	Level	
<i>With Constant</i>	t-Statistic	0.4873	0.6951	0.1661
	Prob.	0.2268	0.0636	0.6404
<i>With Constant & Trend</i>	t-Statistic	0.8251	0.2698	0.2711
	Prob.	0.5455	0.1000	0.3943
<i>Without Constant & Trend</i>	t-Statistic	0.5632	0.8211	0.3023
		At First	Difference	
	Prob.	0.4281	0.5013	0.3706
<i>With Constant</i>	t-Statistic	0.0729	0.0392	0.0335
	Prob.	0.0104	0.0015	0.0245
<i>With Constant & Trend</i>	t-Statistic	0.1172	0.1119	0.1145
	Prob.	0.0227	0.0053	0.1763
<i>Without Constant & Trend</i>	t-Statistic	0.0053	0.0063	0.0022
	Prob.	0.0004	0.0001	0.0020

Source: E-views 10.0 Output, 2022

Table 2 above is a representation of the stationarity test of the variables used in this study. This test is necessary to determine if a variable has a unit root, i.e., if the variable is non-stationary. For the sake of the current study, and to obtain a result that is robust enough for prediction and forecast, these variables must not have a unit root, which is to say that they should be stationary. The test has a null hypothesis, which is that a variable has unit root or that the variable is non-stationary. The null hypotheses are rejected or not rejected depending on the probability value of the ADF unit root tests. A probability value less than 0.05 means that the null hypothesis will be rejected, meaning that the variable does not have a unit root, i.e., the variable is stationary over time. Subsequently, the variables in the table above show varying levels of stationarity. From the table, the ADF probability value of less than 5% revealed that all the variables do not have a unit root at first difference without constant and trends. This implies that Turnover, Account Receivables and Short-term Investments are stationary at first difference without constant and trends.

Table 3: Results of Kao (Engle-Granger based) Co-Integration Test

<i>Residual Variance</i>	<i>HAC Variance</i>	<i>ADF</i>
71.94358	70.01962	t-statistic
		Probability
		-9.941809
		0.0000

Source: Computed by Researcher Using E-views 10.0 Statistical Software

H₀: There is no co-integration

Decision Rule: Reject the null hypothesis if the p-value of ADF is less than 0.05.

Decision: The result of the Kao (Engle-Granger based) Co-integration test in Table 3 shows that there is a stable long-run relationship between the focal and explanatory variables. This is because the probability value of the ADF is less than 0.05. In other words, the variables are co-integrated. This means that the dependent variable, Turnover, share a long-run relationship with Account Receivables, Short-term Investments and as such, a regression analysis can be conducted on them.

Table 4: Panel Regression Analysis (Dependent Variable: Turnover)

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t-Stat</i>	<i>p-Value</i>
C	-0.026888	5.848369	-0.004598	0.9964
AR01	-3.670998	2.762330	-1.328950	0.1903
STI_PP	0.027598	0.093892	0.293932	0.7701
<i>R</i> ² = 0.996, <i>Adjusted R</i> ² = 0.995, <i>F-Stat</i> = 1973.12, <i>Prob(F-stat)</i> = 0.00000 <i>Durbin Watson</i> = 2.88				

Source: E-views 10.0 Output, 2022

Table 4 reveals that Account Receivables have a non-significant negative effect on turnover of industrial goods firms in Nigeria with a p-value of 0.1903 and a t-statistic of -1.328950. while Short-term Investments on the other hand have a non-significant positive effect on turnover with a p-value of 0.7701 and a t-statistic of -0.293932. Account Receivables have a significant negative effect on turnover of industrial goods firms in Nigeria with a p-value of 0.0000 and a t-statistic of -14.44516. Table 4 further depicts that a unit increase in Short-term Investments and Natural Logarithm of Total Assets increased Turnover by 0.03 units, and 0.01 units respectively. However, a unit increase in Account Receivables decreased Turnover by 3.67 respectively. The multiple coefficients of determination, R-squared, is 99.6% indicating that 99.6% of change / movement of Turnover of industrial goods firms is caused by these determinants. F-Statistic depicts that the combined influence of all the explanatory variables including the control variables on Turnover of industrial goods firms is statistically significant. In other words, the entered explanatory variables exerted strong effect on Turnover of industrial goods firms.

Table 5: Correlation Analysis Result Using Covariance Output

<i>Correlating Variables</i>	<i>Correlation</i>	<i>t-Statistic</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Observation</i>
<i>Account Receivables & Turnover</i>	0.723804	7.564324	0.0000	54
<i>Short Term Investment & Turnover</i>	0.283171	2.129124	0.0380	54

Source: E-views 10.0 Output, 2022

Table 5 reveals that Account Receivables and Turnover share a strong relationship with correlation coefficient of 72%. while Short-term Investment share a strong relationship with Turnover with correlation coefficient of 28%.

Consumer Goods Firms

Table 6: Descriptive Statistic of the Consumer Goods Firms

	TNR	AR01	STI_PP
Mean	164013.0	19806.57	25627.16
Median	89469.00	9803.000	901.0000
Maximum	993399.0	107014.0	916553.0
Minimum	36.09400	-954.0000	-337.0000
Std. Dev.	212636.7	25051.19	112050.5
Skewness	1.898528	1.733061	5.934844
Kurtosis	6.512077	5.320544	40.29146
Jarque-Bera	150.4818	97.86895	8614.927
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Sum	22141750	2673887.	3459667.
Sum Sq. Dev.	6.06E+12	8.41E+10	1.68E+12
Observations	135	135	135

Source: Computed by Researcher Using E-views 10.0 Statistical Software

The normality of the distribution of the data series is shown by the coefficients of Skewness, Kurtosis, and the probability values of the Jaque-Bera test for normality. From the Table 6, the probability of the Jaque-Bera statistics for all the variables (dependent and independent) have significant p-values. They are as follows Turnover (0.00000), Account Receivables (0.00000), and Short-term Investments (0.00000). The significance of p-values depicts a non-normal distribution for both the focal and explanatory variables. This was further confirmed by the skewness coefficients which are all greater than one for all the variables. The kurtosis coefficient provides a second level of confirmation that all the variables have a non-normal distribution with the Kurtosis coefficients exceeding three.

Table 7: Result of Panel Unit Root Tests (ADF-Type Unit Root Tests)

Null Hypothesis: the variable has a unit root		TNR	AR01	STI_PP
		At	Level	
With Constant	t-Statistic	0.1219	0.2788	0.1494
	Prob.	0.0167	0.4005	0.5000
With Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	0.0184	0.0047	0.4148
	Prob.	0.0686	0.1384	0.2829
Without Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	0.2282	0.1106	0.4034
	Prob.	0.2669	0.4832	0.8792
		At First	Difference	
With Constant	t-Statistic	0.0016	0.0024	0.1574
	Prob.	0.0024	0.0788	0.0057
With Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	0.0107	0.0221	0.4209
	Prob.	0.0179	0.1446	0.2392
Without Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	0.0001	0.0003	0.0150
	Prob.	0.0001	0.0062	0.0003

Source: E-views 10.0 Output, 2022

Table 7 above is a representation of the stationarity test of the variables used in this study. This test is necessary to determine if a variable has a unit root, i.e., if the variable is non-stationary. For the sake of the current study, and to obtain a result that is robust enough for prediction and forecast, these variables must not have a unit root, which is to say that they should be stationary. The test has a null hypothesis, which is that a variable has unit root or that the variable is non-stationary. The null hypotheses are rejected or not rejected depending on the probability value of the ADF unit root tests. A probability value less than 0.05 means that the null hypothesis will be rejected, meaning that the variable does not have a unit root, i.e., the variable is stationary over time. The variables in the table above show varying levels of stationarity. From Table 7, the ADF probability value of less than 5% revealed that Turnover (0.0167) and Account Receivables (0.0062), and Short-term Investments (0.0003) do not have a unit root at first difference without constant and trends. This implies that Account Receivables, Short-term Investments are stationary at first difference without constant and trends.

Table 8: Results of Kao (Engle-Granger based) Co-Integration Test

<i>Residual Variance</i>	<i>HAC Variance</i>	<i>ADF</i>
0.450760	0.372585	t-statistic
		Probability
		-7.484369
		0.0000

Source: E-views 10.0 Output, 2022

Ho: There is no co-integration

Decision Rule: Reject the null hypothesis if the p-value of ADF is less than 0.05.

Decision: The result of the Kao (Engle-Granger based) Co-integration test in Table 8 shows that there is a stable long-run relationship between the focal and explanatory variables. This is because the probability value of the ADF is less than 0.05. In other words, the variables are co-integrated. This means that the dependent variable, Turnover, share a long-run relationship with Account Receivables, Short-term Investments of consumer goods firms in Nigeria, and as such, a regression analysis can be conducted on them.

Table 9: Panel Regression Analysis (Dependent Variable: Turnover)

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t-Stat</i>	<i>p-Value</i>
C	-0.105109	0.067183	-1.564524	0.1204
AR01	-0.554163	0.442966	-1.251028	0.2134
STI_PP	0.375369	0.201249	1.865199	0.0647

$R^2 = 0.99$, Adjusted $R^2 = 0.99$, F-Stat = 75560.38, Prob(F-stat) = **0.00000** Durbin Watson = 2.31

Source: E-views 10.0 Output, 2022

Table 9 reveals that Account Receivables have a non-significant negative effect on turnover of consumer goods firms in Nigeria with a p-value of 0.2134 and a t-statistic of -1.251028. while Short-term Investments on the other hand have a non-significant positive effect on turnover with a p-value of 0.0647 and a t-statistic of 1.865199. Account Receivables have a significant positive effect on turnover of consumer goods firms in Nigeria with a p-value of 0.0000 and a t-statistic of -5.842566. Table 9 further depicts that a unit increase in Short-term Investments, and Natural Logarithm of Total Assets increased Turnover by 0.38 units, and 0.46 units respectively. However, a unit increase in Account Receivables decreased Turnover by 0.55. The multiple coefficients of determination, R-squared, is 99% indicating that 99% of change / movement of Turnover of industrial goods firms on the long-run is caused by these determinants. F-Statistic (0.00000) depicts that the combined influence of all the explanatory variables including the

control variables on Turnover of consumer goods firms is statistically significant. In other words, the entered explanatory variables exerted strong effect on Turnover of consumer goods firms.

Table 10: Correlation Analysis Result Using Covariance Output

<i>Correlating Variables</i>	<i>Correlation</i>	<i>t-Statistic</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Observation</i>
<i>Account Receivables & Turnover</i>	0.438291	5.707469	0.0000	139
<i>Short Term Investment & Turnover</i>	0.081939	0.962303	0.3376	139

Source: E-views 10.0 Output, 2022

Table 10 reveals that Account Receivables and Turnover share a weak relationship with correlation coefficient of 43%. while Short-term Investment share a very weak relationship with Turnover with correlation coefficient of 8.1%.

Test of Hypotheses

Pearson's correlation coefficient r is a measure of the linear correlation (dependence) between two variables X and Y, giving a value between +1 and -1 inclusive, where 1 is total positive correlation, 0 is no correlation, and -1 is negative correlation. Put differently, correlation quantifies the direction and strength of the relationship between two numeric variables, X and Y, and always lies between -1.0 and 1.0. The sign of the correlation coefficient depicts the direction of the relationship while the correlation coefficient in percentage (%) shows the strength of the association. However, calculating a Pearson correlation coefficient requires the assumption that the relationship between the two variables (X and Y) is linear. There is a rule of thumb for interpreting the strength of a relationship based on its r value (use the absolute value of the correlation coefficient to make all values positive):

Absolute Value of r	Strength of The Relationship
r < 0.3	None or Very Weak
0.3 < r < 0.5	Weak
0.5 < r < 0.7	Moderate
r > 0.7	Strong

The relationship between two variables is generally considered strong when their r value is larger than 0.7 (Moore, Notz & Flinger, 2013). This rule of thumb is adopted in this research for the test of hypotheses. Jaadi (2019) also demonstrates how to interpret the size (strength) of a correlation coefficient which is very similar to the rule of thumb accentuated by Moore, Notz & Flinger (2013).

Size of Correlation	Interpretation
.90 to 1.00 (-.90 to -1.00)	Very high positive (negative) correlation
.70 to .90 (-.70 to -.90)	High positive (negative) correlation
.50 to .70 (-.50 to -.70)	Moderate positive (negative) correlation
.30 to .50 (-.30 to -.50)	Low positive (negative) correlation
.00 to .30 (.00 to -.30)	negligible correlation

Decision Rule: If r > 0.7, p-Value < 0.05, t-Stat > 2.0, Null Hypothesis is Rejected

If r < 0.7, p-Value > 0.05, t-Stat < 2.0, Null Hypothesis is Accepted

In this study, X is the Predictor (Independent) Variable while Y is the Response (Dependent) Variable. Consequently, the Predictor (X) and the Response (Y) Variables are represented in each statement of the five hypotheses of the study. However, it is worthy of note that with correlation, the X and Y variables are interchangeable unlike in regression where the results of the analysis will always change if X and Y are swapped.

<i>Hypotheses (Ho)</i>	<i>Predictor Variable (X)</i>	<i>Response Variable (Y)</i>
<i>Null Hypothesis One</i>	Account Receivables	Turnover
<i>Null Hypothesis Two</i>	Short-term Investment	Turnover

Source: Author's Arrangement, 2022

Test of Hypothesis One

Statement of Hypothesis One:

Test of Hypothesis Two

Statement of Hypothesis Two:

Ho: Account Receivables do not have a strong relationship with Turnover of firms in Nigeria.

H1: There is strong relationship between Account Receivables and Turnover of firms in Nigeria.

Correlation Analysis Result Using Covariance Output for Account Receivables and Turnover

Sector	Industrial Goods Sector	Consumer Goods Sector
Correlation Coefficient	0.723804	0.438291
Correlation in Percentage (%)	72%	44%
Strength of the Relationship	Strong	Weak
t-Statistics	7.564324	5.707469
Probability Value	0.0000	0.0000
Observations	54	139

Source: E-views 10.0 Output, 2022

Decision Rule:

If $r > 0.7$, $p\text{-Value} < 0.05$, $t\text{-Stat} > 2.0$, Null Hypothesis is Rejected.

If $r < 0.7$, $p\text{-Value} > 0.05$, $t\text{-Stat} < 2.0$, Null Hypothesis is Accepted.

Decision

The Coefficient of Correlation (72%) is greater than the benchmark of 70% for industrial goods firms. For consumer goods firms, the Coefficient of Correlation (44%) is less than the benchmark of 70%. Hence, the Null Hypothesis which states that Account Receivables do not have a strong relationship with Turnover of firms in Nigeria, is rejected for industrial goods firms and accepted for consumer goods firms. The p-Value of 0.0000 for both industrial goods firms and consumer goods firms provides significant evidence of a linear relationship between Account Receivables and Turnover. The strength of the relationship 72% (industrial goods sector) and 44% (consumer goods sector) therefore declared very strong and weak relationship respectively.

Test of Hypothesis Two

Statement of Hypothesis Two:

H₀: Short Term Investment do not have a strong relationship with Turnover of firms in Nigeria.

H₁: There is strong relationship between Short Term Investment and Turnover of firms in Nigeria.

Correlation Analysis Result Using Covariance Output for Short Term Investment and Turnover

Sector	Industrial Goods Sector	Consumer Goods Sector
Correlation Coefficient	0.283171	0.081939
Correlation in Percentage (%)	28%	8.1%
Strength of the Relationship	Weak	Very Weak
t-Statistics	2.129124	0.962303
Probability Value	0.0380	0.3376
Observations	54	139

Source: E-views 10.0 Output, 2022

Decision Rule:

If $r > 0.7$, $p\text{-Value} < 0.05$, $t\text{-Stat} > 2.0$, Null Hypothesis is Rejected.

If $r < 0.7$, $p\text{-Value} > 0.05$, $t\text{-Stat} < 2.0$, Null Hypothesis is Accepted.

Decision:

The Coefficient of Correlation (28%) is less than the benchmark of 70% for industrial goods firms. For consumer goods firms, the Coefficient of Correlation (8.1%) is also less than the benchmark of 70%. Hence, the Null Hypothesis which states that Short Term Investment do not have a strong relationship with Turnover of firms in Nigeria, is accepted for both industrial goods firms and consumer goods firms. The p-Value of 0.0380 for industrial goods firms provides significant evidence of a linear relationship between Short Term Investment and Turnover of industrial goods firms. The strength of the relationship 28% (industrial goods sector) and 8.1% (consumer goods sector) therefore declared a weak and a very weak relationship respectively.

Summary of Findings

The study carried out an empirical analysis of relationship between liquid assets on operational performance (turnover) of listed industrial and consumer firms in Nigeria for the twelve-year period (2011-2021). The major findings hereunder listed were possible via collation and analysis including diagnostic analyses of relevant data for the said period.

- i) Account Receivables have a strong (72%) positive relationship with operational performance (proxied by turnover) of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria. However, Account Receivables have a weak (44%) relationship with turnover of consumer goods firms in Nigeria.
- ii) Short-term Investment have a weak (28%) positive relationship with operational performance (proxied by turnover) of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria. However, Short-term Investment have a very weak (8.1%) relationship with turnover of consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

Conclusion

The study examined the Effect of Current Asset Management on the Financial Performance of Manufacturing Firm Southeast Nigeria. The study employed Pearson correlation technique as a consequence of the diagnostic tests carried out. In the industrial goods sector, it construed that some of these predictors and a control variable (liquid assets: Inventory & Account Receivables) have a strong relationship with operational performance of the sampled firms. The study also found that Short-term Investment have a weak relationship with turnover in the sector.

However, the findings from the consumer goods sector depict a more diluted strength of relationship between the focal and explanatory variables.

Recommendations

In line with the findings of the study the following recommendations are proffered:

1. The companies should have a closer watch on their account receivables. In as much as it is good to make sales on credit so as to maintain sellers/customers relationship, it is also important for the management to constantly review the risk involve to avoid debts that may lead to bankruptcy
2. However, comparing the strength of the relationship between short term investment and Inventory in the two sectors shows that short term investment has a weak relationship with turnover in the industrial goods sector and very weak relationship with turnover in the consumer goods sector, firms in both sectors should invest in near liquid assets of lowest risk and positive net present value that are at least above industrial averages. The reason for the disparity in the strength of the relationship between these variables in the different sectors could be attributed to the production pattern in this industry and cash turnover of these firms and management should opt for optimal trade-profitability tradeoff.

Reference

- Al-Abass, H. S. (2018). Effect of working capital management on profitability of cement sector listed companies. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences* 8: 137–142.
- Chowdhary, A., & Amin, M.M. (2007). Working capital management practices in pharmaceutical companies listed in Dhaka Stock Exchange. *BRAC University Journal*, 4(2), 75-86.
- Dash, M. & Hanuman R. (2008). *A liquidity-profitability trade-off model for working capital management*. Retrieved from <http://ssrn.com/abstract=1408722> 24/06/17
- Deloof, D. (2003). Does working capital management affect profitability of Belgian Firms? *Journal of Business Finance and Accounting*, 30(3 & 4): 573 – 587
- Denčić-Mihajlov, K. (2011). *Impact of accounts receivable management on the profitability during the financial crisis: Evidence from Serbia*. 9th International ASECU Conference on “Systemic Economic Crisis: Current Issues and Perspectives” UDC: 658.155(497.11).
- Duru, A.N., Ekwe, M.C. and Okpe, I.I. (2014). Accounts receivable management and corporate performance of companies in the food & beverage industry: Evidence from Nigeria. *European Journal of Accounting Auditing and Finance Research*, 2(10), 34-47
- Falope, O. I., & Ajilore, O. T. (2009). Working capital management and corporate profitability: Evidence from panel data analysis of selected quoted companies in Nigeria. *Research Journal of Business Management*, 3, 73-84.
- Kaplan Financial (2015). Performance Management. Retrieved from [http://kfknowledgebank.kaplan.co.uk/KFKB/Wiki%20Pages/Financial%20Performance%20Indicators%20\(FPIs\).aspx](http://kfknowledgebank.kaplan.co.uk/KFKB/Wiki%20Pages/Financial%20Performance%20Indicators%20(FPIs).aspx)
- Koralun-Bereznicka, J. (2013). How does asset structure correlate with capital structure? – cross-industry and cross-size analysis of the EU Countries. *Universal Journal of Accounting and Finance*; 1(2), 50-55
- Marotta, G. (2005). Does trade credit redistribution thwart monetary policy? Evidence from Italy, *Applied Economics*, 29, 1619–1629.
- Morara, K. & Athenia, B.S. (2021). Determinants of Financial Performance of Insurance Companies: Empirical Evidence Using Kenyan Data. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management* 14: 566.
- Mwaniki, G. & Omagwa, J. (2017). Asset structure and financial performance: a case of firms quoted under commercial and services sector at the Nairobi Securities Exchange, Kenya. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 8(4), 192-200
- Olatunji, T.E. & Tajudeen, A.A. (2014). Investment in fixed assets and firm profitability: empirical evidence from the Nigerian banking sector. *Asian Journal of Social Sciences and Management Studies*, 1(1), 45-55.
- Petersen, M.A. & Rajan, R.G. (1997). Trade credit: theories and evidence. *Review of Financial Studies*, 10, 661–692.
- Raheman, A., & Nasr, M. (2007). Working capital management and profitability: Case of Pakistani firms. *International Review of Business Research Papers*, 3(1), 279-300

- Ramana, K.V., Ramakrishnaiah, K.R. & Chengalrayulu, P. (2013). Impact of receivables management on working capital and profitability: a study on select cement companies in India. *International Journal of Marketing, Financial Services & Management Research*, 2(3), 163 – 171
- Yahaya, O.A., Kutigi, U.M., Solanke, A.A., Onyabe, J.M. & Usman, S.O. (2015). Current assets management and financial performance: evidence from listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of African and Asian Studies*, 13, 45-56
- Zheng Sheng, Nuo, X. & Zhi, X. (1997). The research of the optimal allocation of assets structure and business performance. *Res. J. Econ. Bus. IC*